

ASSESSMENT OF ARTISANAL FISHING GEARS AND CRAFTS IN DUTSIN-MA RESERVOIR, KATSINA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

*Fishing gear and crafts are equipment used in catching fish and navigation in water body. The socio-demographic characteristics of fishermen, types of fishing gears and craft utilized, the common fish species caught as well as challenges faced by the fishermen was studied at Dutsin-ma reservoir. Thirty (30) structured questionnaire was distributed to fishermen in the study area. Data collected were subjected to descriptive statistics. The result showed that all the respondents were male (100%) and married (82.6%). Higher percentage (65.2%) has a household size of 1-5 between the age of 46 and 55 years. The fishermen (69.6%) are relatively experienced with having 15 and above years of experience and (69.6%) operating on part time basis. The commonly used gears and craft are cast net, hook and line, gillnet, Malian trap and Gourd. The dominant species in the catch are *Oreochromis niloticus* and *Bagrus bayad* respectively.*

KEYWORDS

Craft, Gears, Fishing, Fishermen and Reservoir

1. INTRODUCTION

Fish refers to an organism such as finfishes, mollusks, shellfish, and other aquatic inhabitants. They are a significant sources of animal protein, particularly in the tropical regions of a developing countries, and are easily accessible and affordable to humans (FAO, 2020). Fish serve as a rich source of essential amino acids, minerals and fatty acids that are important for ensuring a balanced diet. It is also a vital source of economic growth in a country and serves as a means of livelihood for numerous individuals (Salele *et al.*, 2023). Tools used for collecting and capturing fishery resources from different bodies of water are known as fishing gears (Dienye and Olopade 2017). Fishing gears differs mostly in the materials (fibre, metal, plastics etc.) used in their construction, structure, mode of operation (passive or active) and principles of capture process (hooking, entangling, filtering, trapping etc.). Numerous types of fishing gears are constructed using various technologies and methods use in operating them (Obinna *et al.*, 2018). These gears are classified as active and passive used to catch target fish species primarily for commercial value and domestic consumption (Rodulf *et al.*, 2019). Fishing gears of various types have been utilized for many years to capture fish in reservoirs, wetlands, lakes, and other bodies of water (Bonjoru *et al.*, 2019). The most significant industry, artisanal fisheries, provides the majority of the fish supply in developing nations. However, the low technology, outdated equipment, inadequate funding for expansion, and other characteristics of artisanal fishing make it a labor-intensive industry with little to no chances for growth (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2009). According to Nwabeze and Erie (2013), artisanal fishermen in Nigeria make use of unsustainable fishing practices and do not have adequate knowledge of sustainable fishing practices resulting in fish shortage across the country. Several researchers have surveyed the different fishing gears and crafts in Nigerian water bodies (Kwen and Kingdom, 2013; Emmanuel, 2009). Decision-making in fisheries management, especially with regard to technical measures in fisheries regulations,

requires a thorough grasp of the characteristics, uses, and functions of the main fishing gear and techniques (Obinna *et al.*, 2018). There is no available literature on the fishing gears utilized by artisanal fishermen in Dustin-ma Reservoir in Katsina State of Nigeria. This study will therefore, provide the baseline information that will assist and contribute to the literature on the types of fishing gears and crafts which will further contribute to the fishery management in the study area.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study area

This study was conducted in Dustin-ma Reservoir of Katsina State located in Dustin-ma headquarters of Dustin-ma LGA, Katsina State. Dustin-ma Reservoir is situated on latitude $12^{\circ} 28' 0.7''\text{N}$ and longitude $7^{\circ} 29' 56''\text{E}$ in Dustin-ma town of Katsina State. It was built in 1974 to accommodate the domestic needs of people in Dutsin-ma. It is a repository of tributaries from Darawa-Korama, Hadari-Korama from the western and eastern side of the reservoir respectively as well as from the run-off from the surroundings. It has only one active landing site where all fishermen thrive for the postharvest handling processes.

Figure 1: Map of Dutsin-ma reservoir

2.2. Sampling procedure

Thirty (30) artisanal fishermen were randomly selected at the Dustin-ma Reservoir for the period of the study.

2.3. Data collection

The data for this research was collected through the deployment of structured questionnaire to access information from thirty (30) artisanal fishermen from the study site between May and August 2024.

2.4. Data Analysis

The data obtained was subjected to descriptive statistics (mean and percentages) using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS, version 20).

3. RESULTS

All the sampled fishermen in Dutsin-ma reservoir are males between ages of 46-55 (30.4%) and 25-35 (26.1%) while 36-45 accounts for (17.4%). 82.6% are married with household sizes of 1-5 (65.2%), while 38.4% have Qur'anic and (34.8%) have first school leaving certificate and majority of them (69.6%) are full time fishermen where majority of them (69.6%) do not belong to any co-operative society and (30.4%) are members of the cooperative society. Those with fishing experience of 15 years and above are the majority (69.6%), followed by those with the fishing experience of 11-15(21.7%) while those with the fishing experience between 1-5 years are the least (4.3%).

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of fishermen in Dutsin-ma reservoir.

Socio-demographic characteristics	Variables	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	100
Age		
	25-35	26.1
	36-45	17.4
	46-55	30.4
	56-65	13.0
	65above	13.0
Marital status		
	Single	8.7
	Married	82.6
	Widow	8.7
Number of households		
	1-5	65.2
	5-10	30.4
	10-15	4.3
Education level		
	No education	21.7
	First school leaving certificate	34.8
	Quranic education	34.8
	Senior school education	4.3
	tertiary education	4.3
Fisher's status		
	Full-time	30.4
	Part-time	69.6
Cooperative societies membership		
	Member	30.4
	Non member	69.6
Fishing experience		
	1-5	4.3
	6-10	4.3
	11-15	21.7
	15 above	69.6

Majority of the fishermen have fishing gears (82.6 %) and gourd (82.6%) being the most used craft in Dutsin-ma reservoir. The cost of fishing gourd ranges between 11,000-20,000 (47.8%) and 35,000 and above. Most of the fishermen have been using their fishing gourd for 1-5 years (60.9%) and few of the fishermen (21.7%) used their gourds for 5-10 years, while (17.4%) of the fishers don't have gourd. And most the fishermen in Dutsin-ma reservoir (91.3%) use 1-5 fishing gourds while few of the fishers (8.7%) use 5-10 gourd majorly obtained through purchase (97.5%).

Table: 2 fishing craft specification

Fishing craft specification	Variables	Percentage
Number of fishing gear	Yes	82.6
	No	17.4
Type of craft	Gourd	82.6
	None	17.4
Cost of fishing gears	5000-10000	4.3
	11000-15000	26.1
	16000-20000	21.7
	21000-25000	8.7
	26000-30000	13.0
	31000-35000	4.3
	35,000 and above	4.3
	None	17.4
	Duration of using own craft	
	1-5 yrs.	60.9
	5-10 yrs.	21.7
	None	17.4
Number of fishing craft	1-5	91.3
	5-10	8.7
Source of fishing craft	Others	4.3
	Purchase	97.5

Majority of the fishermen in Dutsin-ma reservoir Katsina state Nigeria (91.3%) uses gillnet (locally refers to as 'Kalli'), cast net (*Bargi*), Malian trap (*Mali*) and hook & line ('*Kugiya*'), while some among them (4.3%) use cast net and hook & line and some of them (4.3%) use cast net, Malian trap and gill net, where majority of the gears (69.6%) sizes are 2.5-3 inch and the remaining gears (30.4) sizes are 1.5-2.5 inches. It was reported by most of the respondents (52.2%) at the study area that they use their gears from only 1-5yrs, while some (47.8%) use it for almost 6-10yrs. All the fishermen (100%) reported purchase as the source of their fishing gear in the study area. The duration of the use of the gears by the respondents recorded 1-5yrs (95.7%) as the majority years the gears stays with the fishermen, while few among them (4.3%) reported the use of their gears from the range of 6-10yrs. Majority of the fishermen in the study area (52.2%) reported that tilapia is their targeted species followed by *Clarias* (34.8%) and *Bagrus bayad*. Two fish species were observed to be the most dominant fish species caught by the fishermen of the Dutsin-ma reservoir. *Oreochromis niloticus* (95.7%) and *Clarias* sp (4.3%) and *Bagrus bayad* has the highest numbers of catch where almost all the respondents (82.6%) in the study area prefer to catch the *Clarias* sp than any other fish species, while few of the fishermen in the study area (17.4%) prefer to catch Tilapia sp because it's the most dominant sp in the study area. Most

fishermen reported that the fish caught is the determining factor (39.1%) while (21.7%) of the respondents said it is the area to be fished, likewise (21.7%) linked it to the cost of fishing gears that determine fishing gear selectivity.

Table: 3 fishing gear specification

Fishing gears use	Variables	Percentage
	Gill net, cast net, Malian trap and hook & line	91.3
	Cast net and hook & line	4.3
	Cast net, Malian trap and gillnet	4.3
Mesh size		
	2-2.5 inch	30.4
	2.5-3 inch	69.6
Number of fishing gear(s) own		
	1-5	52.2
	6-10	47.8
Source of fishing gear		
	Purchase	100.0
Duration of using own gear		
	1-5 yrs.	95.7
	5-10 yrs.	4.3
Targeted species		
	Catfish	34.8
	Tilapia	52.2
	Bagrus	13.0
Most abundant Specie caught		
	<i>Tilapia</i>	95.7
	Cat fish	4.3
Preference of sp., to catch		
	Catfish	82.6
	Tilapia	17.4
Factor that determines the selection of fishing gear		
	Season	13.0
	Fish to be caught	39.1
	Cost of fishing gears	21.7
	Safety at operation	4.3
	Area to be fished	21.7

All the sampled fishermen in Dutsin-ma reservoir agreed (100%) that they face challenges in their fishing activities, where high cost of fishing materials unanimously agreed to be the most faced challenge by the respondents. Some of the faced poaching of craft, gears or catches (34.8%), while majority (65.2%) don't encounter it. Fish spoilage rate was identified to happen less (65.2%) than those that spoil (34.8%) in the study area. Poor durability of fishing materials was reported in the study area (95.7%) while few (4.3%) agreed to be durable. Inefficiency of the gears used in the study area were reported to be less (60.9%) by the respondents and inability to repair the gears was recorded to be less (91.3%) in the study area. Inability to access credit facilities by the fishermen of the study area were reported to be a problem to most of the fishers (52.2%) while it has no impact to some of them (40.8%). Some of the respondents (65.2%) stated insecurity as one of the challenges faced by the respondents in the study area.

Table: 4 Challenges facing the fishers in the study area

Challenges facing the fishers in the study area	Variables	Percentage
Challenges faced		
	Yes	100.0
Cost of fishing materials		
	Yes	100.0
Stealing of craft, gears or catches		
	Yes	34.8
	No	65.2
Fish spoilage		
	Yes	34.8
	No	65.2
Poor durability of fishing materials		
	Yes	95.7
	No	4.3
Inadequate of fishing materials		
	Yes	43.5
	No	56.5
Gear inefficiency		
	Yes	39.1
	No	60.9
Inability to repair craft and gears		
	Yes	8.7
	No	91.3
Inadequate access to credit facilities		
	Yes	52.2
	No	47.8
Insecurity		
	Yes	65.2
	No	34.8

4. DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic characteristics of the artisanal fishermen in the study area provide an insight into their economic situation. Majority of the fishermen are men, which demonstrates both the perilous nature of the job and the conservative nature of the state (Katsina) with female being restricted to some outdoor activities. These findings are similar to that of [11], who reported male to be the dominating gender in Dutsin-ma reservoir. The fishermen's age and the cultural customs in the study area may have contributed to their marital status and household size, which overwhelmingly showed married status. [12] found that the sociocultural and economic

characteristics of fishermen's households showed significant variation. The highest level of education found in the study area is typical, with a greater focus on primary and Qur'anic education. Although most fishermen are in their prime, their lack of formal education has an impact on their productivity due to their limited access to and capacity to use new technologies [13]. The highest percentage of age group of fishers fell between 46-55 years, which may possibly indicate that, the youth are fascinated by fishery practices in or face increasing difficulties to join the sector. Much along the same lines, [14], reported the fisherman in Niger State, Nigeria's Borgu local government area is between the ages of 30 and 49. The fact that the fishermen are full-time and experienced suggests that they have been in the business for a long time, making it an important source of income for the local population. It is also similar to [9], who also reported that fishing activities are mostly done by people within the age range of 30 to 40 years. This distribution may be the result of younger people being more willing to try new fishing operations or fisheries practices, being more mentally alert and adaptable to new ideas in fishing gear development techniques and running their own businesses without experiencing issues that older people face. The results of the present study also revealed that craft uses by the fishers are mostly gourds, this could be as a result of the water size and their low cost compared to the canoe or motorized ones. These findings are not in-line with findings of [14] that reported the use of both gourds and canoes in Ajiwa dam, Jibiya dam and Zobe dam respectively which are all in Katsina state. This indicates that other water bodies in Katsina state are advanced than Dutsin-ma reservoir in terms of fishing activities since 17.4% has no gourd at all. Majority of the fishermen in Dutsin-ma reservoir Katsina state Nigeria uses gillnet, cast net, Malian trap and hook & line which is similar to the findings of [14] who reported gill nets, cast nets, traps and hook and line to be the dominant fishing gears in Ajiwa dam, Jibiya dam and Zobe dam respectively which are all in Katsina state. Moreover, the most commonly used artisanal fishing gears in the study area is cast net which disagrees with the findings of [15] that reported other types of gears such as hook and line, malian/gura, clap net and giwa net in Northern Nigeria. The higher lifespan of fishing gears observed in the study area is attributed to the low level of operation and fish species diversity in the reservoir. *Oreochromis niloticus* is the most dominant fish species in Dutsin-ma reservoir, followed by *Clarias gariepinus* then *Bagrus bayad*. Which is expected considering the prolific, parental care and adaptive nature of *Oreochromis niloticus*, this is supported by the findings of [17] & [18] that found *Oreochromis niloticus* to be the most dominant specie in Zobe reservoir, Ajiwa reservoir, and Jibiya reservoir, respectively. The results of the fish catch revealed that most fishermen preferred catching African catfish due to its high market value in Dutsin-ma town. However, only three (3) families were reported which is generally low diversity and poorly distributed in the reservoir compared to other water bodies in the state. The very few numbers of families reported can be associated with the gear's preference and socio-economic characteristics of fishers. The relationship between gear types and sociological and economic status of fishermen coexists in the study area as reported that, fishermen use their resources to purchase fishing gears and crafts with no support from the government or any organization. All the sampled fishermen in Dutsin-ma reservoir agreed that they face one challenge or the other in fishing activities. High cost of fishing materials occurs most of the time, stealing of craft and gears, poor durability of fishing materials, lack of access to credit facilities and insecurity are the major challenges faced by the respondents in the study area. Challenges confronting the fishers highlighted are identical in other inland water bodies, within Nigeria and other developing countries of the world.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The fishing gears and crafts used in the study area are to capture different fish species. The most prominent of the gears and crafts observed are Cast net and gourd respectively. These are selected since they are suitable for the water body and the target species. The active age of the responded can be categorized as youthful. The majority of fishing gears are modified with the

express purpose of capturing the intended species. The study areas is characterized by extremely low fish diversity and most likely low income.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. There is need for extension services to educate the fishermen on improved fishing gears and fishing practices to be adopted.
- ii. A thorough stock assessment is required in order to fully explore the water body's potential using a variety of sophisticated and locally available fishing gear.
- iii. Easy and accessible credit facilities should be introduced to the fishers to intensify their fishing business.

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Short Biography